

INTERACTIVE STRATEGIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

N.I. Rahmatova

School №23 of Gijduvan district, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Abstract: *The article discusses interactive methods of teaching English. The possibility of using some of these methods and techniques in English lessons is described. Interactive learning method increases motivation in learning English, the learning process becomes more interesting and entertaining.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, training, communication motivation, interest, skills.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, information and communication technologies are widely used in the education system, as well as in other industries. Conducting classes with the use of new pedagogical technologies requires the teacher to have the highest intellectual ability. Education can be transformed only when the teacher can accurately identify the interests of students, correctly direct them on the path to achieving the goal. The teacher's use of interactive methods in their classes contributes to the development of a real environment of competition and cooperation.

Interactive learning is a specific form of organization of cognitive activity, which aims to create a comfortable learning environment in which each student feels comfortable, confident, considers himself successful, intelligent and believes in himself. The essence of interactive learning is that the learning process takes place under the condition of constant, active positive interaction of all students. When the teacher and student are equal [1, 2].

2. PROPOSED INTERACTIVE METHODS

Role-playing is a speech, game and educational activity at the same time.

From the point of view of students, role - playing is a game activity in which they act in different roles. For the teacher, the goal of the game is the formation and development of speech skills and abilities of students. The role-playing game is manageable, its educational character is clearly understood by the teacher. Since role-playing is based on interpersonal relationships, it causes a need for communication, stimulates interest in participating in it in a foreign language, i.e., it performs a motivational and motivational function. Role-playing is largely determined by the choice of language tools, contributes to the development of speech skills and abilities, and allows students to model communication in various speech situations. In other words, it is an exercise for mastering skills and abilities in the context of interpersonal communication. In this regard, the role-playing game provides a learning function. There are a huge number of forms of role-playing games in English lessons: presentations, interest clubs, interviews, correspondence trips, round tables, press conferences, excursions, fairy tales, reports, etc. As the results of training show, the use of role-playing games in foreign language lessons contributes to positive changes in students' speech both in qualitative terms (a variety of dialogical units, initiative of speech partners, emotionality of utterance) and in quantitative terms (correctness of speech, volume of utterance, pace of speech). game provides a learning function. There are a huge number of forms of role-playing games in English lessons: presentations, interest clubs, interviews, correspondence trips, round tables, press conferences, excursions, fairy tales, reports, etc. As the results of training show, the use of role-playing games in foreign language lessons contributes to positive changes in students' speech both in qualitative terms (a variety of dialogical units, initiative of speech partners, emotionality of utterance) and in quantitative terms (correctness of speech, volume of utterance, pace of speech) [2, 3].

"The effectiveness of this technology is obvious because the project has become one of the most active forms of interactive learning and development of

communication skills in English lessons. This method is aimed at developing active independent thinking of the child and teaches him not just to remember and reproduce the knowledge that he receives, but to be able to apply it in practice. Working on a project requires a high level of individual and collective responsibility for each project development task. Technology "working in a group".

Group work provides an opportunity for all students to participate in the work, as it allows them to practice collaboration and interpersonal skills, which makes it one of the most popular strategies. All this is often impossible in a large team. This is an integral part of many interactive methods, such as mosaics, debates, public hearings, and almost all types of simulations.

Technology "Mosaic". The text of the information is divided into chunks. Individual pieces of information are served to students in a scattered form. The task is to collect the full text of the information. Each student reads their own piece, and then make up the full text, based on what they heard.

The "Sociological survey" technology aims to collect information on the proposed topic and involves the movement of students throughout the class. They get sheets with questions and tasks written on them. Alternatively, it is possible to propose the following assignment: Find out what movies you like to watch your classmates. Ask as many guys as you can. In this case, the question "What films do you like to see?" is worked out, the answer to which often causes difficulties for students, since it requires a complete answer. Snowball technology"

This technique is well used for the development of speech and memory of younger students. The student names the item and passes the baton to the neighbor, who comes up with a second word related to the same group of items, and calls two words in order. The next student names two words and adds their own, and so on.

You can work out vocabulary on the following topics:" Toys"(I have a teddy bear, a doll, a dog...)," Clothes "(I have a shirt, a sweater, ...)," Fruits and vegetables "(I like oranges, bananas, apples).

Advantages of using interactive learning methods: - activate all students; -fun and interesting;

- increases motivation to learn;
- allows you to diversify the forms of work in the classroom;
- allow you to apply your knowledge in practice; -teach independent work;
- develop mental activity; - develop the ability to work in a team;
- allow you to identify different points of view;
- foster a culture of communication;
- facilitate the perception of new material;
- stimulate cognitive activity;
- increase self-esteem and satisfaction from their work;
- they teach you to listen, understand, and respond to the other person. Thus,

the essence of interactive learning is that the learning process is

organized in such a way that almost all students are involved in the process of learning, they have the opportunity to understand and reflect on what they know and think. Joint activity of students in the process of learning, mastering the educational material means that everyone makes their own special individual contribution, there is an exchange of knowledge, ideas, and methods of activity [4, 5].

All of the above technologies are not used in isolation. There is an active process of their integration. Integrated learning technology is fundamental in English lessons. Integrated lessons do not differ from traditional lessons in types and forms. These are lessons in the formation of skills and abilities, lessons in their development, lessons in their application in practice, and lessons in control and verification. The difference is that all types and forms of integrated lessons imply a fairly large information block in the lesson itself or independent work on solving a problem. Based on my experience, I can say that studying the material in small blocks does not lead to the formation of a knowledge system. The process of conscious, deep assimilation of the material slows down. Integrated learning technology allows you to make the process of learning English more effective. Here, this technology is

implemented through the use of various methods and forms of work. Before proceeding to their description, I want to note that my main task as a teacher, I see in teaching children the skills to independently extract the necessary information, analyze the knowledge obtained and apply it to solve new problems. To do this, I use several methods described below in my work [5].

3. CONCLUSION

The teacher should not stop there. It must constantly develop, engage in self-education, so that the knowledge received by students meets the requirements of modern society and education, including. Information and communication technologies offer great opportunities for teachers who are looking for additional tools to solve their professional tasks.

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